

NASA Cit Sci Eclipse Project Resources

Dear NASA Cit Sci Champions!:

Thank you for sharing these opportunities with the people at your SunSpot eclipse event!

This packet contains all the documents you need to prepare yourself to answer questions and to effectively connect people with project opportunities that work for them.

Printed reference material for you (feel free to make and distribute copies of any of these!):

Day-of-Eclipse Projects comparison table with QR codes
Eclipse Megamovie summary
GLOBE Eclipse Overview English
SunSketcher summary
Eclipse Soundscapes summary
Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Observer Role Facilitation Quick Start Guide - *fill in the location and Eclipse Maximum fields on the Field Notes Form to display for attendees to copy!*

Additional resources can be explored at <https://science.nasa.gov/citizen-science/>.

Display:

The **“Do you have a few minutes”** 2-pager is your copy of a poster that should be (👉) displayed at your site. The three projects featured on this poster are the ones that are easily joined the day of the eclipse. **It’s a good idea to download apps and review the project in advance!** Each project requires an app download or provides info online.

The **2-page NASA Citizen Science Flyer** presents all the ongoing research projects in Earth Science, Planetary Science, Heliophysics, Astrophysics, and Biological and Physical Sciences (supporting life in space) that need volunteers! It is printed for 2-pages for easy display on a table top. Please let people know that there are projects they can join any day of the year.

An Eclipse Soundscapes Observer Field Notes Form with the location information and Eclipse Maximum time filled out!

Lat and long in decimal degrees: Open a smartphone map app, place a pin (hold your finger somewhere until one appears), move the pin as near as you can to where you are, release your finger, and scroll down. You’ll find lat and long displayed.

Time of Eclipse Maximum: Use the QR Code on the Field Notes Form!

Hand-out:

Eclipse-Day-Observation-Field-Notes-Form. The Eclipse Soundscapes project can be done without technology, however, it does require that folks have the field notes form. No training is required. Do help people fill out the location and Eclipse Maximum data fields!

May the weather gods smile on you!

Sarah Kirn sarah@gmri.org

<p>Investigate eclipse impacts on physical environment</p>	<p>Investigate eclipse impacts on life (bugs, animals, people)</p>	<p>Investigate the shape of the Sun using the Moon as a reference</p>	<p>Investigate dynamics of the Sun's plasma plumes, which are only visible in total eclipse</p>
<p>Download required</p>	<p>"Field Notes" paper helpful!</p>	<p>Download required</p>	<p>Instructions & camera requirements online</p>
<p>Use your phone and an external thermometer</p>	<p>Submit via social media and/or ES website after the eclipse</p>	<p>Occupies your phone during eclipse</p>	<p>Use your own DSLR camera, 300 mm lens, tripod, GPS location data</p>
<p>13 years old and older</p>	<p>Any age, family-friendly</p>	<p>13 years old and older</p>	<p>18 years old and older</p>

Eclipse Megamovie 2024

The Sun's corona – its outermost atmosphere – writhes and twists and throws off plumes of hot plasma. Measuring the motion of these plumes could help scientists understand the nature of the corona: what makes it so hot, and how it creates space weather. But these plumes can only be directly observed during an eclipse.

Volunteer with Eclipse Megamovie 2024 and on April 8 you can help scientists answer persistent questions about the Sun's corona and its plasma plumes!

What you'll do:

- Use your own DSLR (mirrorless) camera to capture images of totality to share as an **Observer** or **Science Team Alpha Recruit (STAR)**!
- Use your Python coding skills to help with the Machine Learning Analysis for the Eclipse Megamovie after the eclipse!

Requirements

- **Time:** Photographers: 6 hours on eclipse day, plus training. Image processors: 2 to 5 days.
- **Equipment:**
 - STARS: DSLR (or mirrorless) camera, 300mm to 500mm lens depending on sensor size, tracking mount, tripod, and GPS location information.
 - Observer: DSLR (or mirrorless) camera, 300 mm lens, tripod, and GPS location information.
 - Image processors: a web-connected computer.
- **Knowledge:** Training is provided for STAR photographers. Python coding experience is required to participate in image processing.

Get started as an Observer

- Visit the project website for details on equipment
- On April 8: Photograph the eclipse! And also:
 - Take flats and darks (calibration shots)
 - Include location data with your photographs (as metadata)
 - Upload your RAW photographs to the EM2024 website

Visit <https://eclipsemegamovie.org/> to learn about:

- The science behind Eclipse Megamovie and what the team hopes to learn with your help.

Eclipse Megamovie 2024 is part of the Heliophysics Big Year, NASA's celebration of heliophysics, the science of the Sun and how it influences Earth, space, and the planets in our Solar System.

Follow the QR code to the right to learn about more NASA research projects that need your help. **Everyone, regardless of citizenship status, is invited to join these projects!** science.nasa.gov/citizen-science

WHO: Age 18 and up
WHERE: outside on eclipse path on April 8; online after April 8
DIVISION: Sun
LAUNCHED: 2023

The red and blue band that arcs north from Mazatlán, Mexico to San Antonio, Texas all the way to northern Maine and across Newfoundland, Canada marks the “path of totality” for the April 8 2024 eclipse. This is the path from which people on Earth can witness a complete eclipse of the Sun. Outside of this path, observers may see a partial eclipse, with the amount of the Sun being blocked by the Moon decreasing with distance from the path. Interactive map available at http://xiubier.free.fr/en/site_pages/solar_eclipses/TSE_2024_GoogleMapFull.html Credit: Xavier M. Jubier

The two images above were made by volunteers Bill Ingalls (left) and Carla Thomas (right) during the 2017 total solar eclipse as part of the 2017 Eclipse Megamovie project.

The Eclipse Megamovie Team includes

Laura Peticolas Principal Investigator	Thomas Targett Co-Investigator	Hunter Mills Data Scientist (ML/AI)	Hannah Hellman Communication Specialist/ Editor
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Observe the Total Solar Eclipse with GLOBE Observer

National Aeronautics and Space Administration

Save the date for the total solar eclipse on April 8, 2024!

Explore the Sun-Earth connection by observing what happens to our atmosphere during the solar eclipse on April 8, 2024.

The Sun drives many processes in Earth's atmosphere. During an eclipse, the Moon casts a shadow on the Earth's surface. In the shadow, the air temperature drops and clouds that are fueled by the heat of the Sun may begin to dissipate. With just a smartphone and a thermometer, you can help us better understand the complex relationship between the Sun and Earth.

Get the App

Download the GLOBE Observer app onto a smartphone or tablet by scanning the QR code or going to observer.globe.gov/get-the-app.

Don't worry if you don't see the Eclipse tool in the app yet; it will become available closer to the eclipse. You will only see the tool if you are in an area that will experience a partial or total eclipse.

Set up an account and complete the tutorials for Land Cover and Clouds before the day of the eclipse.

Find a Thermometer

You will need a thermometer to collect air temperature data.

You can use a digital or liquid-filled thermometer. However, the weather app on your phone is not a substitute for a thermometer.

Gather everything you need to safely observe the eclipse, such as water, sunscreen, eclipse glasses, and anything else you need to stay safe and comfortable during the eclipse.

Remember, looking directly at the Sun without proper eye protection is unsafe EXCEPT when the Moon completely blocks the Sun. This happens ONLY within the narrow path of totality. Outside the path of totality, it is NEVER safe to look directly at the Sun without a solar filter.

Set-up Your Thermometer

Place your thermometer in a shaded, but well-ventilated area. For example, you can place your thermometer under a chair or hold it in your own shadow. Be sure to hold the thermometer away from yourself or other sources of heat.

Using the App

You do not need a connection to the internet to record observations. The app will walk you through all of the steps.

Next Observation:
4 mins 45 secs

Clouds

Would you like to perform a clouds observation now?

NO

YES

The app will remind you when it is time to take the next observation.

Collect Data

Your observations are most useful to scientists if you collect data through all phases of the eclipse (about 2 hours before and after maximum eclipse).

When you first arrive, document the land cover around you.

Take photos of the landscape in each direction. Include your thermometer in one photo.

The land cover affects the way that solar energy is absorbed.

Every 15-30 minutes, or any time you notice a change in the clouds, observe the clouds and sky conditions.

Cumulus clouds are fueled by the heat of the Sun. If these clouds are present before the eclipse, they may dissipate as the Moon blocks the Sun.

Every 5-10 minutes, measure the air temperature.

Use your thermometer to measure air temperature and enter the data into the app.

We can expect the temperature to drop as the moon blocks the Sun's energy.

Share Your Observations

The app will generate a graph of your data, which you can share on social media. Remember to send in your observations after the eclipse. All GLOBE data is made freely available to researchers and students around the world.

Follow us for updates!

TheGLOBEProgram

GLOBEProgram

globeprogram

SunSketcher

Our Sun is not quite a perfect sphere. Knowing our Sun's true shape would give scientists new clues about its mysterious interior and test theories of gravity. But precisely measuring the shape of this enormous, nearly-round object has been challenging - until now.

Join the SunSketcher team and help make these measurements during the total solar eclipse on April 8, 2024! The SunSketcher app on your smartphone will capture images of Baily's Beads. Baily's Beads are the last glimmers of sunlight that slip through the valleys of the Moon as it eclipses the Sun and the first rays of sunlight to sneak through the low spots on the other side of the Moon as the Sun re-appears.

Anyone in the path of totality with a smartphone is invited to participate on April 8, 2024!

What you'll do:

- Be part of an historic effort to calculate the shape of the Sun.
- Enjoy the eclipse while your smartphone collects data for science.

Requirements

- **Time:** 5-10 minutes to download app and read the instructions, plus the time you spend watching the eclipse.
- **Equipment:** An Android or Apple smartphone running the free SunSketcher app and a tripod or material to position your phone to face the Sun.
- **Knowledge:** None. The app provides instructions.

Get started!

- Visit the project website and sign up to join the team and be notified when the app is available.
- While you're there, check out the app tutorial (view full screen for best results).
- Make a plan to be in the path of totality for the April 8, 2024 eclipse - with your phone and the SunSketcher app!

Visit the project website

<https://sunsketcher.org> (or QR code at right) to learn about:

- The science behind the SunSketcher project and
- The Heliophysics Big Year, NASA's yearlong celebration of heliophysics, the science of the Sun and how it influences Earth, space, and the planets in our solar system.

Follow the QR code to the right to learn about more NASA research projects that need your help. **Everyone, regardless of citizenship status, is invited to join these projects!**
science.nasa.gov/citizen-science

WHO: Age 13 and up

WHERE: Outside, in the path of totality for the April 8 eclipse

DIVISION: Sun

LAUNCHED: 2023

The three screenshots above are from the SunSketcher App tutorial, available on the website. They outline three key steps to follow to use your phone to contribute to the SunSketcher project. Images from <https://sunsketcher.org/app-tutorial.php>

This image illustrates Baily's Beads - the bright spots of light on the Moon's edge that are visible at the very beginning and the very end of totality. The Moon's surface is covered with mountains, valleys, and craters, which make the edge of the Moon bumpy. The low points are the last - and first - places where sunlight passes as the Moon eclipses the Sun. In this picture, multiple images taken in succession show that the beads disappear and appear in stages, with only the very deepest valley and craters allowing sunlight to shine through closest to totality. This illustration is composed of a series of images taken from ESO's La Silla Observatory on 2 July 2019 during a total solar eclipse by P. Horálek/ European Southern Observatory.

The SunSketcher Team includes:

Hugh Hudson Science Advice & Eclipse Guru
Gordon Emslie Principal Investigator
Greg Arbuckle Co-Investigator
Michael Galloway Co-Investigator

Eclipse Soundscapes

How do the sudden darkness and temperature changes of a solar eclipse impact life on Earth? Eclipse Soundscapes invites you to document changes in the environment during the week of the April 8, 2024 total solar eclipse, using your own senses or an audiomoth sound recorder.

Anyone in or near the path of the April 8, 2024 total solar eclipse path is invited to participate. Your observations will reveal how animals and insects respond to dramatic changes in their environment. All project resources - including those for educators - are provided in multiple formats to support accessibility and inclusion.

Include the Eclipse Soundscapes Project at your Eclipse Day event! Check out the **Quick Start Guide** on the project website..

What you'll do:

- Observe and report your multi-sensory observations of a solar eclipse.

Requirements

- **Time:** 1-3 hours, depending on role you choose
- **Equipment:** No equipment required for Apprentice or Observer roles. Data Collector role requires an AudioMoth device, a MicroSD card a plastic bag, zip ties and a return envelope.
- **Knowledge:** None. Tutorials on project website provide all instruction needed for each role.

Get started! Visit the project website for details.

- Learn about eclipses with the Apprentice Training (available in English and Spanish).
- Be an ES Observer on eclipse day using your own senses, then submit your observations to the ES website! (no equipment needed; available in Spanish).
- Interested in scientific tools and audio recording? Be an ES Data Collector.

Visit the project website

<https://eclipsesoundscapes.org/> (or QR code at right) to learn about:

- Companion curriculum,
- The 1935 study that inspired this project,
- Animal and insect behaviour you might observe during the solar eclipse, and
- The Heliophysics Big Year, NASA's yearlong celebration of heliophysics, the science of the Sun and how it influences Earth, space, and the planets in our solar system.

Follow the QR code to the right to learn about more NASA research projects that need your help. **Everyone, regardless of citizenship status, is invited to join these projects!** science.nasa.gov/citizen-science

WHO: All ages

WHERE: Outside during the April 8 solar eclipse

DIVISION: Sun

LAUNCHED: 2023

Caption: Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collectors deploy AudioMoth audio recorders like the one this man is holding, and mail them in after the Eclipse.

Credit: Eclipse Soundscapes

Insects like the grasshopper in the image above change their behavior near sunset - typically, they start to sing. How will they behave during an eclipse? This project wants to know what you hear during the eclipse!

Credit: Ihor Hvozdetzkyi: Royalty-free stock photo ID: 1630876729

The Eclipse Soundscapes Team includes:

Henry "Trae" Winter
Chief Scientist,
ARISA Lab
Co-Founder

MaryKay Severino
Education
Director, ARISA
Lab Co-Founder

Kelsey Perrett
Writer/Com
munications

Joel Goncalves
Developer

Tracey Kline
Educator &
Consultant

William Alexander
Web
Developer

Will Oestreich
Soundscape
Ecologist

Regine Gilbert
Industry Assistant
Professor/ UX/UI
Specialist

Help Your Community Be Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Observers Quick Start Guide

The purpose of this guide is to provide April 8, 2024 Total Solar Eclipse event and activity organizers (such as Library Staff, Park Rangers & Staff, NASA Sun Spot organizers, etc) with a quick and easy overview of the Eclipse Soundscapes Project and a ready-to-go handout to print and provide to the general public attending your total solar eclipse events so that they can easily facilitate community participation in ES.

Title Page

Page 1: ES Overview & Tips for ES Observer Role Implementation at Large Events

Pages 2 & 3: Front/Back Participation Handout (English)

Pages 4 & 5: Front/Back Participation Handout (Spanish)

The Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science Project is supported by
NASA award No. 80NSSC21M0008

Eclipse Soundscapes Observer Activity

How do solar eclipses affect animals & insects?

The Eclipse Soundscapes Project Overview

The Eclipse Soundscapes Project is a [NASA Citizen Science](#) project funded by [NASA Science Activation](#) that is studying how solar eclipses affect life on Earth during the 2023 annular eclipse and the April 8, 2024, total solar eclipse. Eclipse Soundscapes will revisit an eclipse study from almost 100 years ago that showed that animals and insects are affected by solar eclipses! Like this study from 100 years ago, ES will ask for the public's help. ES will also use modern technology to continue to study how solar eclipses affect life on Earth!

We need the public's help to gather as much observation data as possible! Eclipse Soundscapes is collecting multisensory observations from the April 8, 2024 total solar eclipse. The observations and sound data collected will help us understand the impact of 2023 and 2024 solar eclipses on various U.S. ecosystems.

Facilitator Training

- Complete Observer Training (20-30 min) <https://eclipsesoundscapes.org/observer/>
- Review Science behind Eclipse Soundscapes <https://eclipsesoundscapes.org/es-csp-science/>

Implementation Tips

1. Print out the two-page (front/back) Eclipse Soundscapes Observer Role Field Notes to Handout to hand out to event attendees.
2. Add the Eclipse Maximum Start time to the handout for your area or have information readily available and on display.
3. Participants will need to use their mobile devices to find latitude & longitude (DD). Be ready to share how-to info (<https://eclipsesoundscapes.org/location-reporting-format/>)

FAQs

What kinds of observations is ES looking for?

What nature sounds and sights do you observe? Do nighttime animals and insects appear and get louder? How about daytime animals and insects? And remember, people are animals too!

How do I submit my observations?

After you observe and take notes during the 10 minutes before eclipse maximum, during eclipse maximum, and the 10 minutes after eclipse maximum, use your notes to help you fill out the online ES Observer submission form at <https://eclipsesoundscapes.org/observer/>.

Eclipse Soundscapes Observer Activity

How do solar eclipses affect animals & insects?

Date: _____ Location: _____

Latitude & Longitude (DD) _____

Location Type: (urban / suburban / country) _____

Location Description: (forest, park, lakefront, etc) _____

How many people are nearby? _____

Eclipse Maximum

Weather: _____

Time: _____

Observation Start Time: _____ Observation Stop Time: _____

(For 10+ minutes) Before Eclipse Maximum (Hear / See / Feel) - Species? behavior?

Insects	Birds	Amphibians
Mammals	Reptiles	People/vehicles

During Eclipse Maximum (Hear / See / Feel) (Hear / See / Feel) - Species? behavior?

Insects	Birds	Amphibians
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Eclipse Soundscapes Observer Activity

How do solar eclipses affect animals & insects?

Mammals	Reptiles	People/vehicles

(For 10+ minutes) After Eclipse Maximum (Hear / See / Feel) - Species? behavior?

Insects	Birds	Amphibians
Mammals	Reptiles	People/vehicles

Additional Observations / Notes:

Submit your observations so they can be included in the Eclipse Soundscapes Project & receive an Observer Certificate!

EclipseSoundscapes.org/Observer

Observador de Eclipse Soundscapes - Notas de campo

¿Cómo afectan los eclipses solares a los animales y los insectos?

Fecha: _____ Ubicación: _____

Latitud y Longitud (DD) _____

Tipo de ubicación: (urbana/suburbana/rural) _____

Descripción de la ubicación: (parque, frente a un lago, etc.) _____

¿Cuántas personas hay cerca? _____

Hora de inicio del
máximo del eclipse: _____

Clima: _____

Hora de inicio de la observación: _____ Hora de fin de la observación: _____

(Para más de 10 minutos) Antes del máximo del eclipse (oír/ver/tocar) -

¿Especie? ¿Comportamiento?

Insectos	Aves	Anfibios
Mamíferos	Reptiles	Gente/vehículos

Durante el máximo del eclipse (oír/ver/tocar) - ¿Especie? ¿Comportamiento?

Insectos	Aves	Anfibios
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Observador de Eclipse Soundscapes - Notas de campo

¿Cómo afectan los eclipses solares a los animales y los insectos?

Mamíferos	Reptiles	Gente/vehículos

(Para más de 10 minutos) Después del máximo del eclipse (oír/ver/tocar) -
¿Especie? ¿Comportamiento?

Insectos	Aves	Anfibios
Mamíferos	Reptiles	Gente/vehículos

Otras observaciones/Notas:

¡**Envíe sus observaciones** para que puedan incluirse en el Proyecto Eclipse Soundscapes y reciba un Certificado de Observador!
EclipseSoundscapes.org/Observer

EclipseSoundscapes.org is supported by NASA award No. 80NSSC21M0008

Do **YOU** have a few minutes to do **NASA Eclipse Science?**

How do eclipses affect weather?

observer.globe.gov/do-globe-observer

Eclipse Soundscapes

eclipsesoundscapes.org

Seeking observers to record
changes around them.
How do eclipses affect the natural
world? Use their form to **observe**
during the eclipse and upload later.

Sunsketchers

sunsketcher.org

Taking cell phone photos
of the Baily's Beads
for science!
The goal is to more precisely work
out the actual size of the Sun
from the visible beads that relate
precisely to the exact geographic
lineup between the observer,
craters on the moon's edge,
and the eclipsed Sun.

*Use the app to observe with
a smartphone during totality
and upload later.*

Can you track temperature and clouds during the eclipse along with NASA's GLOBE Observer app?

observer.globe.gov/do-globe-observer

Would you like to be an Observer with Eclipse Soundscapes and report multisensory observations?

Best suited for those out in nature,
but everyone can try it and record what
they notice. There is a Notes form and
then afterwards you fill out an online
form and receive a certificate.

eclipsesoundscapes.org

Are you in the path of totality with a cell phone?

Then your phone can snap critical pictures
of Bailey's Beads (bright spots at the beginning
and end of totality) that the NASA funded
SunSketchers project can use to more precisely
figure out the SHAPE of the SUN. Set in a
safe place and enjoy the eclipse.

sunsketcher.org

Do NASA Science

Researchers, ready to lead a science project with volunteers?

Scan this QR code.

Educators, looking for authentic science activities for your learners?

Scan this QR code.

Ready to do real, cutting-edge science now?

NASA needs your help! Scan the QR code above and pick a project!

LOVE NASA? LOVE SCIENCE? VOLUNTEER TO DO REAL NASA SCIENCE!

NASA's volunteer scientists are searching NASA data for new worlds, asteroids, and comets. They are tracking the impacts of climate change on lake levels, coral reefs, and mosquito populations. Hundreds of volunteers have co-authored publications in professional journals. Many have made new, lasting friendships with NASA scientists and with one another. Scientific discoveries made by NASA volunteers include:

- Hundreds of extrasolar planets
- Thousands of brown dwarf stars
- 100,000s of emperor penguin nests
- Most of the known comets
- A new kind of aurora phenomenon

Our volunteer projects, sometimes called “citizen science” projects are open to everyone around the world, and not limited to U.S. citizens or residents. They aim to teach you everything you need to know as you go along - so don't worry if you never studied science or forgot what you learned in school. Pick one and try it out!

Just be ready: there are no guaranteed results, and sometimes the answers will remain unknown. But if you're tired of just reading about other people's groundbreaking discoveries and ready to get involved, visit science.nasa.gov/citizenscience or click on the links below.

Projects with the require no prior knowledge, experience, or special tools beyond a computer or smartphone. Other projects may involve going to a specific location or using tools such as a backyard telescope.

Astrophysics

- Are We Alone In The Universe - arewealone.earth
- Backyard Worlds: Planet 9 - backyardworlds.org
- Dark Energy Explorers - www.zooniverse.org/projects/erinmc/dark-energy-explorers
- Disk Detective - diskdetective.org
- Exoplanet Watch - exoplanets.nasa.gov/exoplanet-watch
- Planet Hunters TESS - planethunters.org
- Planet Patrol - exoplanetpatrol.org
- Unistellar Network Investigating TESS Exoplanets (UNITE) - science.unistellaroptycs.com

Biological and Physical Sciences

- Growing Beyond Earth - fairchildgarden.org/gbe

Image Credits:

Top: credit: Allison Cusick

Bottom left: credit: NASA

Bottom right : credit: HamSCI

www.nasa.gov

Earth Science

- Air Quality Citizen Science - aqcitizenscience.rti.org/#/
- Community Snow Observations - communitysnowobs.org
- Fjord Phyto - fjordphyto.ucsd.edu
- Floating Forests - floatingforests.org
- Fresh Eyes On Ice - fresheyesonice.org
- GLOBE Observer: Clouds, Eclipse, Land Cover, Mosquito Habitat Mapper, Trees - observer.globe.gov/do-globe-observer
- Lake Observations by Citizen Scientists and Satellites - locss.org
- Landslide Reporter - gpm.nasa.gov/landslides/index.html
- Mapping Application for Penguin Populations and Projected Dynamics (MAPPPD) - penguinmap.com
- Mountain Rain or Snow - www.rainorsnow.org
- NeMO-Net - nemonet.info
- Spritacular - spritacular.org
- Soundscapes to Landscapes - soundscapes2landscapes.org
- Chesapeake Water Watch - serc.si.edu/citizen-science/projects/chesapeake-water-watch

Heliophysics

- Aurorasaurus - aurorasaurus.org
- Goldstone Apple Valley Radio Telescope (GAVRT) - gavrt.lewiscenter.org
- HamSci - hamsci.org
- Radio Jove - radiojove.org
- Solar Jet Hunter - www.zooniverse.org/projects/sophiemu/solar-jet-hunter
- Sungrazer Project - sungrazer.nrl.navy.mil
- Heliophysics Audified: Resonances in Plasmas (HARP) - listen.space-science.org
- Solar Active Region Spotter - www.zooniverse.org/projects/eimason/solar-active-region-spotter

Planetary Science

- Active Asteroids - www.zooniverse.org/projects/orionnau/active-asteroids
- Catalina Outer Solar System Survey - www.zooniverse.org/projects/fulsdavid/catalina-outer-solar-system-survey
- Cloudspotting on Mars - www.zooniverse.org/projects/marek-slijski/cloudspotting-on-mars
- International Astronomical Search Collaboration (“Isaac”) - iasc.hsutx.edu
- Jovian Vortex Hunter -
www.zooniverse.org/projects/ramanakumars/jovian-vortex-hunter
- JunoCam - www.missionjuno.swri.edu/junocam

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Eclipse Soundscapes Observer- Field Notes

How do solar eclipses affect animals & insects?

Date: _____ Location: _____

Latitude & Longitude (DD) _____

Location Type: (urban / suburban / country) _____

Location Description: (forest, park, lakefront, etc) _____

How many people are nearby? _____

← Eclipse Maximum

Weather: _____

Start Time: _____

Observation Start Time: _____ Observation Stop Time: _____

(For 10+ minutes) Before Eclipse Maximum (Hear / See / Feel) - Species? behavior?

Insects	Birds	Amphibians
Mammals	Reptiles	People/vehicles

During Eclipse Maximum (Hear / See / Feel) (Hear / See / Feel) - Species? behavior?

Insects	Birds	Amphibians
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Eclipse Soundscapes Observer- Field Notes

How do solar eclipses affect animals & insects?

Mammals	Reptiles	People/vehicles
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(For 10+ minutes) After Eclipse Maximum (Hear / See / Feel) - Species? behavior?

Insects	Birds	Amphibians
Mammals	Reptiles	People/vehicles

Additional Observations / Notes:

Submit your observations so they can be included in the Eclipse Soundscapes Project & receive an Observer Certificate!
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